

The uncertain impacts of overshooting 1.5°C on carbon stocks and productivity in terrestrial ecosystems

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41 **Abstract**

42 Overshoot scenarios, in which global temperatures peak and then decline through emission
43 reductions and CO₂ removal, are increasingly central to climate policy as we are already
44 approaching 1.5 °C warming. Yet the ecological reversibility of such pathways remains poorly
45 understood, even though the trajectories of productivity and carbon stocks in terrestrial
46 ecosystems have major implications for land-based carbon sink projections.

47 Here we draw on four complementary lines of research to study the land carbon sink under
48 overshoot: (i) CMIP6 models, which project declines in Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP)
49 after peak warming. Nevertheless, NEP remains positive, leading to a stabilization of terrestrial
50 carbon stocks (cLand). However, model spread is large, with different models projecting strong
51 increases or marked declines in cLand. (ii) A systematic review on global change experiments,
52 which identified 256 papers (warming, drought, irrigation or elevated CO₂, all elements of an
53 overshoot scenario). However, only 15 included a recovery phase following treatment. This
54 reveals a gap in experimental design for understanding ecosystem responses under overshoot
55 conditions. Where recovery was assessed, responses were mixed, with persistent legacy effects
56 documented particularly after drought. (iii) Modern-day overshoot analogues, with two El Niño
57 events and the 2018–2020 European droughts showing that compound heat and drought can
58 cause carbon losses that recover slowly, with repeated extremes progressively reducing
59 ecosystem resilience. (iv) Paleoclimate records from the Holocene Climatic Optimum and the
60 Paleocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum, which further demonstrate that the exceedance of
61 ecological thresholds can trigger vegetation changes and carbon cycle feedbacks that long
62 outlast the climatic perturbation itself.

63 Together, these findings show that the trajectory of the terrestrial carbon sink during climate
64 overshoot is uncertain. Ecosystem responses are often delayed and threshold dependent,
65 suggesting that current projections of reversibility in the land carbon sink during the cooling
66 phase may be too optimistic.

67

68 **Keywords:** temperature overshoot, terrestrial carbon sink, CMIP6, manipulation experiment,
69 climate change

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73 Introduction

74 As global mean temperatures approach 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels (Cannon, 2025;
75 Forster *et al.*, 2025), overshoot scenarios are increasingly considered as plausible climate
76 pathways for eventually meeting the Paris Agreement targets (Schleussner *et al.*, 2016; Hoegh-
77 Guldberg *et al.*, 2019; Meyer and Trisos, 2023; Van Vuuren *et al.*, 2026). In such scenarios,
78 temperatures peak, temporarily exceeding a target (such as 1.5 or 2 °C) before declining
79 through a combination of strong emissions reductions and large-scale carbon dioxide removal
80 (Fig. 1; Mendez *et al.*, 2025; Moustakis *et al.*, 2024; Reisinger *et al.*, 2025). This temperature
81 peak is likely accompanied by drastic changes in precipitation and extreme weather events
82 ((IPCC), 2021; Pfliederer, Schleussner and Sillmann, 2024). Although integrated assessment
83 models often treat these pathways as largely reversible, growing evidence suggests that
84 overshoot raises the risk of crossing critical tipping points in the Earth system (Ritchie *et al.*,
85 2021; Armstrong McKay *et al.*, 2022). This risk is particularly pronounced as the overshoot
86 period gets longer, which increases the likelihood of triggering irreversible changes (Pfliederer,
87 Schleussner and Sillmann, 2024; Schleussner *et al.*, 2024).

88 Understanding the impact of overshoot on terrestrial ecosystems is critical. They absorb
89 roughly a quarter of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, making them a crucial carbon sink
90 (Friedlingstein *et al.*, 2025), yet they also represent the largest source of uncertainty in future
91 climate projections (Canadell *et al.*, 2021; Gier *et al.*, 2024). How a cooling phase of declining
92 temperatures and CO₂ concentrations would affect this sink remains poorly understood. The
93 core concern is hysteresis: rather than recovering symmetrically after peak warming, terrestrial
94 ecosystems may carry persistent legacy effects or be pushed past tipping points from which
95 recovery is impossible (Albrich, Rammer and Seidl, 2020; Wigneron *et al.*, 2020; Meyer and
96 Trisos, 2023). This risk is reinforced by regional climate change, as the changes in regional
97 precipitation and climatic extremes are likely to reverse only partially after global temperatures
98 peak (Pfliederer, Schleussner and Sillmann, 2024; Liu *et al.*, 2025). Moreover, the
99 intensification of extreme events (droughts, storms) during peak warming may drive
100 ecosystems past tipping points before regional cooling can take effect (Armstrong McKay *et al.*
101 *et al.*, 2022; Möller *et al.*, 2024; Ritchie *et al.*, 2026), though tipping of slow-onset elements may
102 be avoided if the magnitude and duration of the overshoot remain limited (Ritchie *et al.*, 2021,
103 2026). Therefore, ecological reversibility during overshoot cannot be assumed, yet it remains
104 a critical gap in the literature.

105 Studying the impact of overshoot on ecosystems is challenging however, as observations of
106 recovery following peak temperatures remain scarce. We therefore consider complementary
107 sources of information in this study. First, Earth System Models (ESMs) offer a global, multi-
108 decadal perspective on land carbon dynamics. However, they were not designed for overshoot
109 trajectories and poorly represent legacy effects and disturbance-recovery dynamics (Armstrong
110 McKay *et al.*, 2022). We can also look at manipulation experiments on global change, which
111 offer mechanistic precision (De Boeck *et al.*, 2015). However, these are typically restricted to
112 single drivers, limited spatial scales and number of species, and short timeframes, meaning
113 slow processes such as species turnover may go undetected (Luo *et al.*, 2011). Modern-day

114 analogues of extreme climatic events provide observational validation but are similarly
115 constrained in duration and scope. Lastly, Paleoclimate records extend the temporal frame to
116 periods of substantial temperature change (Fordham *et al.*, 2020), but no past interval closely
117 mirrors the pace of contemporary warming, and proxies such as pollen and stable isotopes only
118 capture some elements of past vegetation dynamics. Nevertheless, because these limitations
119 are largely non-overlapping, the four approaches together offer a broader picture of what
120 terrestrial ecosystems may face under an overshoot scenario.

121

122 Our primary focus in this comparison is on carbon stocks and productivity in terrestrial
123 ecosystems. This is not to diminish the importance of biodiversity or shifts in species
124 composition (Chapin *et al.*, 1995; Meyer and Trisos, 2023; Metz *et al.*, 2026), which can
125 themselves have substantial impacts on productivity (Morin *et al.*, 2018). However, Earth
126 System Models represent vegetation through fixed plant functional types that preclude ecotone
127 shifts or novel ecosystems, and manipulation experiments and modern-day analogues are too
128 short-lived or coarse to capture compositional turnover. We therefore restrict our primary scope
129 to carbon-related responses, though we draw on paleoclimate records to reflect on longer-term
130 compositional change.

131

132 In this study, we synthesize current knowledge to examine how terrestrial ecosystem
133 productivity and carbon stocks respond under climate overshoot scenarios, with a particular
134 focus on the trajectory during the cooling phase. We integrate evidence from four
135 complementary sources. First, we assess global ESM simulations, while also zooming in on
136 Europe, where extensive observational records and experiments are available, and Africa,
137 where limited data availability makes models the primary tool for evaluating climate change
138 impacts. Second, we conduct a systematic review of global change manipulation experiments
139 to determine whether studies include recovery phases following warming, altered precipitation,
140 or elevated CO₂ treatments, and to assess how ecosystems respond during recovery. Third, we
141 analyse modern-day analogues, studying ecosystem responses to recent climate extremes. We
142 include the 2015-2016 and 2023-2024 El Niño events in tropical forest regions and the 2018-
143 2020 European droughts. Fourth, we examine paleoclimate reconstructions from pollen records
144 and geological archives, which provide a longer-term perspective on ecosystem responses than
145 contemporary observations and experiments alone can capture.

146

147 **Methods**

148

149 **1. CMIP6 model and scenario selection**

150 To assess terrestrial carbon cycle responses under overshoot scenarios at global and regional
151 scales, we analysed output from the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble of Earth System Models.
152 We selected ten models for which output was available for at least three of the four following
153 scenarios: SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, and SSP5-8.5. The list of the models and
154 available scenarios is included as Supplementary Table S1.

155 SSP1-1.9 and SSP1-2.6 were selected because they show a temperature overshoot pathway in
156 most models, which we define as a scenario in which the end-of-century temperature is lower
157 than the maximum temperature reached before 2100 (see Supplementary Fig. S1 for
158 temperature projections per model and Table S2 for the overshoot details). This does not mean
159 that the temperature falls below the Paris Agreement thresholds of 1.5 or 2 °C by 2100, but
160 they all include a temperature increase and decrease around a variable peak. The multi-model
161 mean of SSP1-2.6 only shows a very limited overshoot trajectory, representing almost a
162 stabilization scenario, while SSP1-1.9 shows a stronger overshoot. SSP5-3.4-OS is specifically
163 designed to produce a sharp rise followed by a decline in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations
164 which results in a similar overshoot in temperature in all models. Lastly, SSP5-8.5 was included
165 as a reference high-end scenario and comparison to SSP-3.4-OS: it follows the same trajectory
166 as SSP5-3.4-OS until approximately 2060, after which CO₂ concentrations continue to rise
167 rather than decline.

168 From each global model we extracted three variables: near-surface air temperature (t_{as} , °C),
169 total land carbon stock (cLand, Pg C), and net ecosystem productivity (NEP, Pg C yr⁻¹). We
170 focused on NEP, defined as gross primary productivity (GPP) minus both plant and
171 heterotrophic respiration, because this represents the net carbon retained by the ecosystem and
172 thus the rate of change of the carbon stock, only excluding carbon losses from disturbances like
173 harvests and fires. We compare these three variables to a reference period (anomalies,
174 expressed as ΔT , $\Delta cLand$ and ΔNEP), in order to show the changes in trends relative to the
175 historical baseline. To calculate the global temperature anomaly, the reference period is the
176 pre-industrial period (1850-1900), which is most common in climate reporting. cLand and NEP
177 were compared to 1985-2014 to depict the changes to the more recent past. Analyses were
178 limited to the period up to 2100 because too few model simulations extended beyond this date
179 to allow robust intercomparison. We then looked at consistency among models in their
180 projections of carbon stock and flux reversibility, using inter-model spread as an indicator of
181 uncertainty.

182 In addition to a global analysis, we examined regional responses in two specific areas:
183 northwestern Europe and central Africa (see Fig. S2 for the masks). Europe is a region with
184 extensive data records and experiments, which can be compared to model outcomes, whereas
185 in Africa data scarcity means models are the primary tool and it is essential to better understand
186 how consistent they are. Not all models reported all variables or ran all scenarios; the
187 availability of model output per scenario is summarised in Supplementary Table S2 and Figure
188 S3.

189 **2. Systematic search of recovery in global change experiments**

190 To compile experimental evidence on ecosystem carbon responses to global change, we
191 screened the MESI database (Van Sundert *et al.*, 2023), which collates field-based global
192 change experiments published up to 2022. We restricted our search to field experiments
193 conducted in natural ecosystems, excluding greenhouse, pot, and planted experiments, to focus
194 on conditions representative of natural ecosystems. Since anthropogenic climate change
195 manifests as a combination of many changes including elevated CO₂, higher temperatures, and

196 regional precipitation shifts (IPCC, 2021), we retained experiments manipulating elevated CO₂,
197 warming, drought, or irrigation (individually or in combination), while excluding fertilisation-
198 only and species-richness manipulations. We further restricted response variables to carbon
199 stocks or measures of net primary productivity (NPP). Ideally, we would compare experimental
200 results to modelled NEP directly, as NEP integrates both productivity and heterotrophic
201 respiration. However, few field experiments simultaneously quantify changes in both
202 productivity and heterotrophic respiration, making ecosystem-level NEP estimates rare in the
203 observational literature. We therefore focus on NPP as the best available proxy, while
204 acknowledging that it captures only part of the carbon cycle response. Applying these filters
205 yielded 198 studies spanning 1994–2021.

206

207 To extend coverage beyond 2022, we conducted a structured Web of Science search including
208 literature up to December 31, 2025. We used search terms combining treatment descriptors
209 (warming, temperature, heating; precipitation, drought, rainfall; CO₂, FACE, eCO₂, enrichment
210 experiment) with productivity terms (ANPP, BNPP, soil carbon, fine root increment, biomass
211 increment, net ecosystem productivity). We included all studies reporting on global change
212 experiments using the same inclusion criteria as for the MESI database. In addition, we
213 performed a targeted search for studies explicitly framing their results around recovery, using
214 the terms 'recovery', 'rewetting', 'removal', or 'cooling' in combination with the same
215 productivity terms. This secondary search was designed to capture studies that might not have
216 appeared in the broader treatment-focused query. Together, the two Web of Science searches
217 yielded 58 additional studies on global change experiments as inferred from the title and
218 abstract.

219

220 From all 256 studies on global change experiments we extracted the study location (latitude,
221 longitude), which we used to infer the ecoregion (Dinerstein *et al.*, 2017). We also extracted
222 the treatment, or combinations of treatments, and the treatment duration. We screened all
223 studies for the inclusion of a recovery phase, defined as a period during which measurements
224 continued after the experimental treatment had ended, and included whether the study reported
225 changes in productivity or carbon stock.

226

227 **3. Modern-day analogues**

228 To complement experimental and modelling evidence with observations, we synthesised
229 published literature on ecosystem productivity and carbon stock responses to major recent
230 climate extremes and their aftermath. The first case study focused on the 2015 to 2016 El Niño
231 event, which caused widespread drought and heat stress across tropical forests globally
232 (Burton, Rifai and Malhi, 2018). We also included papers on the 2023-2024 El Niño event.
233 Reflecting well known geographical biases in climate research (Metcalfe *et al.*, 2025), fewer
234 studies are available from Africa than from other tropical regions. We therefore report
235 responses across the tropics while recognising that African forests may respond differently to
236 climate change than the Amazon (Hubau *et al.*, 2020), an important consideration when linking
237 these observations to the modelling case study. The second case study examined the 2018 to
238 2020 multi year drought in northwestern Europe, which strongly affected temperate forests and
239 grasslands (Rakovec *et al.*, 2022). For each analogue, we reviewed studies reporting on

240 ecosystem productivity during and after the extreme event, with a focus on the trajectory and
241 completeness of recovery. These analogues were used to evaluate whether the recovery
242 dynamics from the experimental work as well as those simulated by the CMIP6 models are
243 consistent with observed post-extreme responses.

244

245 **4. Paleoclimate reconstructions**

246 To extend the temporal frame beyond what experiments or modern observations can provide,
247 and to get more insight into potential ecosystem shifts, we draw on past periods of elevated
248 temperatures as illustrative analogues for understanding ecosystem responses under 21st
249 century overshoot scenarios. The first is the Holocene Climatic Optimum (~9 - 5 ka BP), a
250 postglacial interval characterised by warmer and more favourable growing conditions, with
251 temperatures around 0.5 to 1.5°C above the 20th century average in many regions and
252 atmospheric CO₂ concentrations of about 280 ppm, followed by gradual cooling (Dawson *et*
253 *al.*, 2025; Sweeney, Harrison and Vander Linden, 2025). The second is the Paleocene–Eocene
254 Thermal Maximum (PETM, ~56 Ma BP), a more extreme event characterised by rapid global
255 warming of roughly 5°C over 10 to 20 thousand years, followed by a return to background
256 climate conditions over the subsequent approximately 100 thousand years, under atmospheric
257 CO₂ concentrations estimated between 800 and 2500 ppm (Wing *et al.*, 2005; McInerney and
258 Wing, 2011).

259

260 For each period, we examine published evidence for ecosystem shifts during both the warming
261 and subsequent cooling phases to assess whether recovery occurred and on what timescales.
262 While primary productivity and carbon stocks cannot be directly quantified from paleoclimate
263 records, these archives preserve signals of long-term vegetation change that offer a broader
264 perspective on ecosystem resilience than models, experiments or modern observations alone
265 can provide.

266

267 **Results**

268 **Earth system model experiments show relative reversibility**

269 None of the model scenarios project a return of global temperatures below 1.5°C warming by
270 2100 in the multi-model mean (Fig. 2a, Table S2). Still, all scenarios considered here did
271 display a warming followed by partial cooling trajectory, making them relevant for overshoot
272 analysis. The most explicit of these is SSP5-3.4-OS, which was designed as a strong overshoot
273 scenario. It peaks at 2.96 °C warming in 2064 and then ends at 2.54 °C warming by the end of
274 the century (table S2). SSP1-1.9 and SSP1-2.6 follow more gradual trajectories in which net
275 negative emissions emerge from sustained mitigation rather than a sharp peak and decline.
276 Consequently, these scenarios produce smaller overshoots, with peak warming of 2.03°C and
277 2.25°C, respectively (table S2). Only the SSP1-1.9 scenario returns below 2 °C warming by
278 2100, ending at 1.71 °C. SSP1-2.6 peaks later, in 2069, and then declines only minimally,
279 ending at 2.2 °C warming. There is considerable model spread between the different ensemble
280 members, with CanESM5 and CanESM5-1 consistently driving the upper bounds, while MPI-
281 ESM1-2-LR and NorESM2-LM simulate comparatively lower warming across scenarios (Fig.
282 S3).

283

284 Across all scenarios, the multi-model mean shows continued increases in global terrestrial
285 carbon stocks through the mid 21st century, driven by elevated CO₂ concentrations and
286 warming induced increases in productivity and growing season length (Fig. 2b, Gier et al.,
287 2024; Qiu et al., 2023). Carbon stocks continue to rise until approximately 2060, after which
288 ΔNet Ecosystem Production (ΔNEP; Fig. 2c) declines gradually across all overshoot scenarios
289 and becomes negative under SSP1-1.9, indicating productivity below the historical average.
290 Nevertheless, changes in ΔNEP remain relatively modest, reflecting compensating responses
291 in net primary productivity (ΔNPP) and heterotrophic respiration (ΔRh; Fig. S4). In particular,
292 ΔNPP decreases more directly following peak warming, whereas ΔRh remains comparatively
293 stable because it is strongly linked to the existing carbon stock. As a result, ΔNEP declines
294 after peak warming, but only gradually.

295 Despite the declining ΔNEP, absolute NEP remains positive under all scenarios, and none show
296 a pronounced decrease in total land carbon stocks during the cooling phase (Fig. S2). Instead,
297 carbon stocks stabilise or continue to increase slowly after peak warming, implying that much
298 of the carbon accumulated during the warming phase is retained. However, this multi-model
299 mean masks substantial uncertainty among individual models. Some simulate a persistently
300 positive land carbon sink throughout the second half of the century, whereas others already
301 project negative NEP under present day conditions and consequently simulate substantial
302 declines in land carbon stocks (Figs. S2 and S3).

303 Regional projections broadly mirror the global pattern. In Africa, terrestrial carbon stocks
304 remain above recent-past values throughout the century under all scenarios (multi-model mean
305 cLand 1985-2014 = 133 ± 38.3 Pg C), including SSP5-3.4 OS. However, in both SSP5
306 scenarios there is substantial forest loss projected up to around 2040, resulting in lower cLand
307 values compared to the two SSP1 scenarios, which do not include this disturbance (Fig. 2d).
308 Because these forest losses are treated as disturbances, they are not reflected in ΔNEP. After
309 2040, cLand increases again in both SSP5 scenarios, before stabilising and declining slightly
310 following the peak in temperature and the reduction in ΔNEP under SSP5-3.4 OS. Notably, the
311 overshoot pathway relies on large-scale carbon dioxide removal, partly achieved through
312 afforestation and the accumulation of carbon on land (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2020), which may
313 offset declines in terrestrial carbon stocks that would otherwise occur in response to climate
314 change alone. Despite this, the multi-model mean ΔNEP falls below zero in all overshoot
315 scenarios, indicating ecosystem productivity below the historical average.

316 Western Europe shows a similar overall response (multi-model mean cLand 1985-2014 = 72 ±
317 41.7 Pg C), although the smaller land area and lower forest cover result in smaller absolute
318 changes in carbon stocks. Across the region, terrestrial ecosystems maintain a positive NEP
319 under all scenarios (Fig. S2), even as ΔNEP declines below the historical average during the
320 second half of the century (Fig. 2f,g).

321 **Limited experimental data on recovery after overshoot**

322 Our systematic search identified 256 papers on global change experiments implementing
323 elevated CO₂, warming, drought, or irrigation treatments, with drought studies comprising the
324 majority (Fig. 3). Experiments are heavily concentrated in temperate ecosystems across

325 Europe, China, and the United States, leaving major knowledge gaps for tropical and boreal
326 ecosystems, especially in Africa (Fig. 3).

327 From all those studies, only 15 studies reported a recovery phase after the treatment ended. Just
328 one study examined recovery following warming, combined with irrigation, in a grassland
329 ecosystem in Oklahoma (USA). Over the nine months of post-treatment monitoring,
330 productivity remained suppressed, driven by persistently lower soil moisture in previously
331 warmed plots (Sherry *et al.*, 2008). The one other irrigation experiment with a recovery phase
332 also showed productivity increases during treatment in a temperate forest, followed by declines
333 once watering stopped, suggesting physiological acclimation after twelve years of elevated
334 water supply (Vitali *et al.*, 2024). No CO₂-enrichment experiment reported post-treatment
335 responses.

336 Thirteen grass- and shrubland experiments on drought included a post-treatment recovery
337 phase (Fig. 3). Each reported productivity declines during drought, scaling with drought
338 intensity, followed by mixed outcomes upon re-wetting: some studies found full recovery or
339 even overproduction (Albert, Ro-Poulsen and TN, 2011; Ru *et al.*, 2023; Schärer *et al.*, 2025),
340 while others found negative legacy effects persisting for up to two years (Yahdjian and Sala,
341 2006). Several studies also documented community shifts during recovery, with rapid grass
342 regrowth compensating for slower recovery (Luo *et al.*, 2023; Ru *et al.*, 2023).

343

344 **Modern day analogues of overshoot emphasize the importance of multiple stressors**

345 Given the limited experimental evidence on post-treatment recovery, modern extreme events
346 offer a valuable complement to controlled experiments as analogues for ecosystem responses
347 to climatic stress and subsequent recovery (Salomón *et al.*, 2022; Chambers *et al.*, 2025),
348 similar to an overshoot scenario. These events have two key advantages over field experiments:
349 they operate at spatial scales far exceeding those of any manipulative experiment, and they
350 capture the complex interplay of co-occurring stressors, such as heat and drought, that are
351 known to be disproportionately damaging to vegetation (Yao *et al.*, 2023). At the same time,
352 modern extreme events are typically less intense and shorter-lived than the average climatic
353 conditions projected during an overshoot period. As a result, they likely provide a conservative
354 estimate of the risks that ecosystems would face under true overshoot conditions.

355 *Tropical forest responses to El Niño events*

356 The 2015–2016 El Niño produced unprecedented heat and drought across the tropics, driving
357 an estimated decline of 1.3 Pg C in aboveground carbon stocks between 2014 and 2017 due to
358 persistent aboveground carbon losses in Africa (−0.8 to −1.1 Pg C) and America (−0.4 to −0.6
359 Pg C) (Wigneron *et al.*, 2020). Although photosynthesis recovered rapidly once rains returned
360 (Santos *et al.*, 2018), structural recovery lagged behind and remained highly uncertain.
361 Estimates of aboveground carbon stock recovery vary substantially, from 40% recovery of
362 affected forests by 2019 inferred from L-band microwave vegetation optical depth (Yang *et al.*,
363 2022), to full recovery by late 2020 based on microwave satellite data (Fan *et al.*, 2024),
364 and full recovery times up to 2022 suggested by radar analyses (Bai *et al.*, 2026). Modelled

365 productivity recovered to pre-drought levels across 77% of tropical forest area by 2020 (Wu *et*
366 *al.*, 2025). This spread in estimates reflects genuine variation in what is being measured
367 (photosynthetic activity, canopy structure, biomass), but collectively these studies underscore
368 that even a single extreme drought can impose carbon losses that take many years to restore.

369 Additionally, recovery was spatially heterogeneous. It was slowest in heavily stressed and
370 structurally degraded forests, and in transitional ecosystems at the forest-savanna boundary. In
371 the Cerrado in Brazil, stem productivity declined by 58% during the drought event and
372 rebounded only gradually (Matias Reis *et al.*, 2025). African forests showed greater resilience
373 than Amazonian ones, with field and radar data suggesting a stronger capacity to return to pre-
374 drought conditions (Malhi *et al.*, 2018; Bennett *et al.*, 2021; Berenguer *et al.*, 2021). Where
375 recovery did occur, it was partly facilitated by the elevated moisture typical of subsequent La
376 Niña conditions, which compensated for productivity losses incurred during the drought
377 (Takamura *et al.*, 2023; Zuidema *et al.*, 2025). However, repeated drought events progressively
378 erode this capacity, with prior stress reducing a forest's ability to recover from subsequent
379 disturbances (Tao *et al.*, 2022).

380 The 2023–2024 El Niño, though weaker by standard indices, coincided with record global
381 temperatures and produced a tropical carbon sink anomaly comparable in magnitude to 2015–
382 2016, with the tropical land surface acting as a net carbon source in both 2023 and 2024 (Ke *et*
383 *al.*, 2024; Du *et al.*, 2025). In Amazonia, canopy productivity fell to record lows (Yang *et al.*,
384 2025; Buras *et al.*, 2026) and resilience indicators showed marked deterioration, pointing to a
385 slowing of ecosystem dynamics (Bai *et al.*, 2026). The fact that a comparatively weaker El
386 Niño could produce impacts of this scale reflects the degree to which background warming is
387 amplifying the carbon cycle consequences of individual extreme events.

388 Taken together, these two El Niño events illustrate that compound heat and drought produce
389 carbon losses that are slow to reverse, that recovery depends heavily on subsequent climatic
390 conditions, and that baseline warming is likely progressively amplifying the impact of
391 extremes. Under a climate overshoot scenario, vegetation recovery during the cooling phase is
392 therefore unlikely to mirror the trajectory of the warming phase. Lagged structural responses,
393 eroded resilience from repeated stress, and reduced CO₂ fertilization during the descent from
394 peak temperatures all suggest that productivity is unlikely to behave symmetrically during the
395 cooling phase.

396 *Temperate ecosystem recovery to the 2018-2020 European droughts*

397 The summers of 2018–2020 brought an unprecedented sequence of hot, dry years across
398 Central Europe and the North Sea region, causing widespread forest dieback, bark beetle
399 outbreaks, and grassland productivity losses (Buras, Rammig and Zang, 2020; Schuldt *et al.*,
400 2020; Thonfeld *et al.*, 2022). As with the El Niño events, this period offers a natural experiment
401 in compound heat and drought stress, and in the limits of ecosystem recovery when extreme
402 events occur back to back (Zscheischler *et al.*, 2020).

403 The 2018 event was climatically exceptional, with mean growing-season temperatures over 3.3
404 °C warmer than the long-term average across Austria, Germany, and Switzerland, and with
405 negative drought effects impacting productivity in an area roughly 1.5 times larger than in
406 2003, previously considered the worst drought in Europe in 500 years (Buras, Rammig and
407 Zang, 2020; Schuldt *et al.*, 2020). The strongest drought effects were concentrated north of the
408 Alps, where less drought-adapted ecosystems suffered record heat and drying, while
409 Mediterranean ecosystems were comparatively unaffected (Schuldt *et al.*, 2020; Senf and Seidl,
410 2021).

411 Importantly, physiological recovery between the drought events in these years was incomplete.
412 Legacy effects on productivity were detectable up to 2020 (Schuldt *et al.*, 2020; Senf and Seidl,
413 2021; Sturm *et al.*, 2022), with impaired hydraulic recovery leaving trees vulnerable to
414 secondary stressors such as bark beetles and fungal pathogens, meaning mortality continued to
415 accumulate well after the initial event. A Europe-wide assessment confirmed negative impacts
416 evident by sustained tree cover loss even in 2021, which was a climatological average year by
417 itself, and damage persisted through to 2022 (Knutzen *et al.*, 2025). As a result, some forests
418 were reported to be a consistent net carbon source after 2018 at least up to 2023 (Haberstroh *et*
419 *al.*, 2026).

420 These consecutive extreme drought years reveal that ecosystem vulnerability can increase with
421 event frequency (Ohlert *et al.*, 2025; Serrano-León *et al.*, 2025), as damage accumulates
422 through depleted hydraulic and carbohydrate reserves that are not fully replenished between
423 events (McDowell *et al.*, 2008; Arend *et al.*, 2022). This shift from acclimation to progressive
424 degradation resembles a form of tipping behaviour with direct relevance to overshoot
425 scenarios: it suggests that post-overshoot recovery will not be linear, and that consecutive years
426 of extreme stress will erode both ecosystem resistance and resilience, impacting recovery
427 timescales (Serrano-León *et al.*, 2025).

428 **Paleoclimate analogues suggest asymmetric ecosystem responses during cooling phases**

429 A first relevant paleo-analogue for a gradual overshoot-and-return scenario comes from
430 Holocene vegetation dynamics in Europe and North America. Pollen-based reconstructions
431 show that tree cover peaked around 6,500 years before present during the mid-Holocene
432 Climatic Optimum (~9,000 – 5,000 BP) (Dawson *et al.*, 2025; Sweeney, Harrison and Vander
433 Linden, 2025), when orbital forcing produced summer temperatures in mid to high latitudes
434 broadly comparable in magnitude, if not in rate, to currently projected near-term warming. The
435 cooling that followed was associated with a transition towards more open landscapes and
436 declining tree cover across Europe (Thompson *et al.*, 2022; Dawson *et al.*, 2025). Although
437 human land use from approximately 6,000 BP onward may have contributed to this vegetation
438 shift, its early influence is considered limited, given that rapid population growth occurred only
439 within the last 2,000 years (Klein Goldewijk *et al.*, 2017; Sweeney, Harrison and Vander
440 Linden, 2025).

441 This pattern of reduced tree cover during cooling is further supported by model simulations of
442 European forest dynamics following the abrupt 8.2 ka BP cooling event, which was a period

443 of depressed annual temperatures across the Northern Hemisphere caused by a weakened
444 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. In response to this cooling, which lasted a few
445 hundred years, grasses expanded across much of Europe (Li *et al.*, 2019). Notably, those
446 simulations also demonstrated that similar climatic conditions can sustain divergent vegetation
447 compositions depending on the prior state of the system, suggesting strong path-dependency in
448 ecosystem recovery (Li *et al.*, 2019).

449 As an analogue for the risks under a higher degree of warming, the Paleocene–Eocene Thermal
450 Maximum (PETM, ~55,800 ka BP) provides a more extreme but instructive case. This ~5–6
451 °C global warming event, which unfolded over ~10 to 20 thousand years and persisted for
452 approximately 100,000 years, was associated with widespread terrestrial disruption: existing
453 plant communities partially collapsed and pioneer fern-dominated vegetation persisted for
454 millennia across multiple continents (Wing *et al.*, 2005; Korasidis *et al.*, 2022; Rogger *et al.*,
455 2025; Nelissen *et al.*, 2026), with floral expansions towards the poles (Korasidis *et al.*, 2022).
456 Combined model simulations and vegetation reconstructions suggest that warming-induced
457 migration and evolutionary adaptation of vegetation were insufficient to prevent a widespread
458 loss of productivity (Rogger *et al.*, 2025). Recovery of biospheric carbon stocks was lagged by
459 70,000–100,000 years, producing a prolonged perturbation of the global carbon cycle (Rogger
460 *et al.*, 2025). Although the PETM involved temperature anomalies exceeding a realistic
461 modern-day overshoot scenario and caused much higher atmospheric CO₂-concentrations of
462 800–1680 ppm (Meissner *et al.*, 2014), it demonstrates that rapid exceedance of ecological
463 thresholds can produce vegetation state changes and carbon cycle feedbacks that outlast the
464 climatic perturbation by orders of magnitude.

465 Across these different timescales and magnitudes, the paleorecords show that recovery is
466 generally slower than disturbance. Reversibility to a previous ecosystem state depends on
467 whether thresholds have been crossed and whether the biotic context allows reassembly of prior
468 communities. This stands in stark contrast to the implicit symmetry in many model projections
469 and the way overshoot is now incorporated into policy documents, and reinforces the concern
470 that overshoot-driven ecosystem changes may prove far more disruptive and transformative
471 than the temperature trajectory alone would suggest.

472 **Discussion**

473 Under current emission trajectories, getting anywhere close to the Paris Agreement targets will
474 likely require an overshoot pathway (Cannon, 2025; Van Vuuren *et al.*, 2026), in which global
475 temperatures peak before being brought back down through active carbon dioxide removal.
476 Our synthesis suggests, however, that ecological reversibility during the cooling phase cannot
477 be taken for granted. While Earth system models would predict a trajectory where global
478 terrestrial fluxes decrease during the cooling phase but stay positive, leading to a relatively
479 stable carbon stock, evidence from short-term experimental studies, modern climate analogues
480 and the paleorecord consistently points to ecosystem responses that are asymmetric, lagged,
481 and shaped by persistent legacy effects (Anderegg *et al.*, 2015; Yu *et al.*, 2025; Deng, Yu and
482 Chi, 2026).

483 A fundamental challenge in assessing the cooling trajectory is the mismatch between the
484 timescales of ecological recovery and those of the experiments designed to study it. Our
485 systematic search found that only 15 of 257 global change studies included a recovery phase
486 at all, and only one experiment ran for longer than five years. However, consecutive droughts
487 produce stronger and more persistent losses than isolated events (Luo *et al.*, 2023; Zuidema *et*
488 *al.*, 2025), suggesting the existence of a threshold beyond which return to pre-disturbance
489 conditions becomes increasingly unlikely (Ohlert *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, none combined
490 elevated CO₂, temperature change, and altered precipitation regimes simultaneously, reflecting
491 the considerable logistical challenges involved in these studies. However, this matters because
492 ecosystem responses to multiple drivers are frequently non-linear, amplified, or even reversed
493 relative to single-driver expectations (Sherry *et al.*, 2008; Gharun *et al.*, 2026).

494 Evidence from modern extreme events offers some insight into how interacting climatic drivers
495 affect ecosystems. They show that concurrent heat and drought produce damage that
496 accumulates across years (Knutzen *et al.*, 2025; Ohlert *et al.*, 2025), recovery depends on
497 disturbance intervals and ecosystem composition (Sachsenmaier *et al.*, 2024), and increasing
498 extreme event frequency is progressively eroding baseline resilience (Bai *et al.*, 2026). With
499 such events projected to intensify, ecosystems globally may be approaching transition
500 thresholds, for example from forest to shrubland or savanna-like systems, from which recovery
501 is far more difficult than maintaining the original state would have been (Flores *et al.*, 2024;
502 Maes *et al.*, 2024; Wunderling *et al.*, 2026). However, a limitation of modern analogues is that
503 extreme events occur under current CO₂ concentrations rather than the elevated levels that
504 would accompany an overshoot. Since elevated CO₂ enhances water use efficiency (van der
505 Sleen *et al.*, 2015; Walker *et al.*, 2021), ecosystems during an overshoot may be more drought-
506 tolerant than modern analogues suggest. At the same time, overshoot conditions would persist
507 for multiple years rather than occurring as isolated extreme events, allowing impacts to
508 accumulate over time (Tao *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, extreme heat and drought events by
509 themselves are projected to become more intense in a warmer climate (IPCC, 2021), likely
510 contributing to further declines in ecosystem resilience.

511 The paleorecord extends this perspective across longer timescales and larger temperature
512 anomalies, though with the important caveat that past warming unfolded far more slowly than
513 current climate change, allowing more time for adaptation and evolutionary response
514 (Korasidis *et al.*, 2022). Nevertheless, it offers valuable insight into the nature of ecosystem
515 shifts under sustained climatic change, which are likely to be more pronounced under the
516 unprecedentedly rapid warming now underway. Both the Holocene Climatic Optimum and the
517 Paleocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum illustrate that rapid exceedance of ecological thresholds
518 can generate state changes and carbon cycle feedbacks that long outlast the climatic disturbance
519 itself (Dawson *et al.*, 2025; Nelissen *et al.*, 2026).

520 Current Earth system models are limited by the scarcity of modern overshoot examples against
521 which to develop and test their representations of hysteresis and state shifts. This model
522 uncertainty is reflected, for example, in the lack of consistency between models in projecting
523 carbon stocks in the Congo Basin, a region historically underrepresented in observational data.

524 The current aboveground carbon stock in Congo Basin forests is estimated at 36 Pg C (Worden
525 et al., 2026; though note that their spatial extent is about half of the extent in this study). Yet
526 the spread across model projections implies this stock could nearly double or lose around a
527 third of its biomass by 2100, depending on the scenario and model. Disturbance regimes are
528 similarly poorly captured: European forests are projected to face increasing disturbance from
529 fire, bark beetle outbreaks, and wind damage under all warming scenarios, with both the
530 frequency and occurrence of compound disturbances scaling with the degree of warming
531 (Messori *et al.*, 2025; Grünig *et al.*, 2026). Large-scale disturbance converts mature, high-
532 biomass forest to younger, structurally simpler stands with fundamentally different carbon
533 dynamics, a legacy effect that current models do not adequately represent. Ecosystem
534 degradation during both peak warming and the cooling phase could further release additional
535 CO₂ into the atmosphere (Rogger *et al.*, 2025), slowing further cooling in a feedback loop that
536 current global climate projections rarely account for.

537 Future research should focus on these modelling and experimental gaps. A dedicated model
538 intercomparison effort, TIPMIP, is working to better represent tipping point dynamics in Earth
539 system models (Winkelmann *et al.*, 2025), and the scenarios for the next phase of model
540 intercomparison, CMIP7, now include more direct overshoot pathways and exclude the least
541 plausible extremes of the CMIP6 range (Van Vuuren *et al.*, 2026). Vegetation representation
542 in Earth system models is also becoming more sophisticated and thus potentially more realistic,
543 incorporating demographic processes, nutrient limitation, and more realistic disturbance
544 regimes. On the experimental side, the large existing body of global change experiments (Fig.
545 3) could yield further insight if recovery phases were routinely included after treatments end.
546 Targeted research filling geographical gaps, particularly in the tropics, will also be essential.
547 In addition, Ecotron facilities offer a promising framework, as they allow researchers to study
548 interacting drivers under controlled conditions across multiple climate scenarios (Rineau *et al.*,
549 2019; Roy *et al.*, 2021). They are especially relevant given the likelihood that ecosystems will
550 face novel combinations of temperature and precipitation conditions, which can be tested in an
551 integrated way in these facilities (Williams and Jackson, 2007).

552 Taken together, these research lines suggest that the land carbon sink cannot be assumed to
553 remain stable through the peak of a temperature overshoot, nor that productivity will respond
554 symmetrically to declining temperatures. Rather, productivity may decline more rapidly during
555 the cooling phase than it increased during warming, driven by less optimal growing conditions
556 and lag effects of extreme events. This may drive substantial reductions in the land carbon sink.
557 Ecological reversibility should therefore not be treated as a default assumption in climate
558 projections. Further addressing this research gap requires global change experiments that
559 explicitly incorporate recovery phases, alongside Earth system models with improved
560 representations of disturbance legacies, threshold dynamics, and compositional change.
561 Without these, projections of land carbon uptake during the cooling phase of an overshoot may
562 prove over-optimistic.

563
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575

576 **Conflict of interest statement**

577 The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding this work or its publication.

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580 **Figures**

581

582 Figure 1. Schematic of net CO₂ emission pathways and their respective global temperature outcomes.
583 The left panel displays two illustrative emission trajectories of mitigation pathways (blue and orange
584 lines) that achieve net-zero and subsequently net-negative CO₂ emissions. The right panel depicts the
585 resulting temperature change over time relative to a 1.5°C target (horizontal dashed line), representing
586 overshoot scenarios where global temperatures rise beyond the target, peak, and then decline.

587

588 Figure 2: Multi-model projections of global and regional temperature and terrestrial carbon dynamics.
 589 (a) Change in global mean temperature (ΔT) relative to pre-industrial levels. Horizontal dashed lines
 590 indicate the 1.5 °C and 2.0 °C targets. (b) Global change in terrestrial carbon stock (Δc_{Land}) and (c)
 591 Net Ecosystem Production (ΔNEP), both relative to the contemporary baseline 1985-2014. (d, e)
 592 Regional projections for Central Africa and (f, g) Western Europe showing Δc_{Land} and ΔNEP ,
 593 respectively. Solid lines represent the multi-model mean for four scenarios: SSP1-1.9 (dark blue), SSP1-
 594 2.6 (light blue), SSP5-3.4-OS (yellow), and SSP5-8.5 (red). Shaded areas illustrate the spread across
 595 the model ensemble. Across all plots, box plots show the median and interquartile range of end-of-
 596 century values per scenario.

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Figure 3: Global distribution and biome classification of climate change experiments. (a) Geographic distribution of experimental sites, where pie chart size reflects the number of studies (sites within 600 km are aggregated for visibility) and pie colors indicate the proportion of each treatment type: Drying (yellow), Irrigation (blue), Warming (red), and CO₂ (green). Country borders are sourced from the Rnatural-earth R package (Massicotte and South, 2017) and may not reflect internationally recognized boundaries. (b) Close-up views of the three regions with the highest experimental density; note that marker size is not proportional to study count here to reduce overlap. (c) Number of studies per treatment type and biome, colored by biome classification (see legend); hatching indicates experiments that included a recovery phase.

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898 **Supplementary Material**

899 **Table S1:** Overview of selected CMIP6 Earth system models. Listed models include institution, native
 900 nominal atmospheric resolution, available scenarios, and corresponding reference.

Model	Centre (country)	Native nominal resolution (atm.)	Scenarios available	Reference
CanESM5	CCCma (Canada)	500 km	SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Swart et al. 2019
CanESM5-1	CCCma (Canada)	500 km	SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Sigmond et al. 2023
IPSL-CM6A-LR	IPSL (France)	250 km	SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Boucher et al. 2020
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR	EC-Earth (Europe)	250 km	SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-8.5	Doscher et al. 2022
NorESM2-LM	NCC (Norway)	250 km	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Seland et al. 2020
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	MPI-M (Germany)	250 km	SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP5-8.5	Wieners et al. 2023
CESM2-WACCM	NCAR (USA)	100 km	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Danabasoglu et al. 2020
ACCESS-ESM1-5	CSIRO (Australia)	250 km	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Ziehn et al. 2023
CMCC-ESM2	CMCC (Italy)	100 km	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Lovato et al. 2023
AWI-ESM1-REcoM	AWI (Germany)	250 km	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-3.4-OS, SSP5-8.5	Danek et al. 2025

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903 **Table S2:** Temperature overshoot characteristics for selected SSP scenarios. Peak temperature
 904 represents the multi-model ensemble mean maximum warming anomaly (°C) and the year in which it
 905 occurs, while end-of-century (EOC) temperature refers to the ensemble mean warming in 2098. The
 906 table further shows the timing and persistence of exceedance of the Paris Agreement (PA) warming
 907 thresholds of 1.5°C and 2.0°C. “First exceeded” indicates the first year in which the ensemble mean
 908 surpasses the threshold, “Duration” (yr) denotes the cumulative number of years above the threshold,
 909 and “Below by end of century?” indicates whether warming remains above the threshold continuously
 910 through 2098.

Scenario	Peak T (°C)	Peak year	EOC T (°C)	PA threshold (°C)	First exceeded	Duration (yr)	Below by end of century?
SSP1-1.9	2.03	2046	1.71	1.5	2019	80	Yes
				2	2037	10	No
SSP1-2.6	2.25	2069	2.2	1.5	2024	75	Yes
				2	2047	52	Yes
SSP5-3.4-OS	2.96	2064	2.54	1.5	2024	75	Yes
				2	2037	62	Yes
SSP5-8.5	5.81	2098	5.81	1.5	2024	75	Yes
				2	2037	62	Yes

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Scenario ■ SSP1-1.9 ■ SSP1-2.6 ■ SSP5-3.4-OS ■ SSP5-8.5

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Figure S1. Multi-model projections of global and regional absolute Net Ecosystem Production (NEP), instead of Δ NEP relative to the historical period as shown in Figure 2. Solid lines represent the multi-model mean for four scenarios: SSP1-1.9 (dark blue), SSP1-2.6 (teal), SSP5-3.4-OS (yellow), and SSP5-8.5 (red). Shaded areas illustrate the uncertainty range across the model ensemble. NEP is defined as Gross Primary Productivity minus autotrophic and heterotrophic respiration; positive values indicate a carbon sink, while negative values indicate the land is a net source of carbon to the atmosphere.

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Figure S2. Geographical boundaries of the selected study regions. (A) Central Africa (15°S–10°N, 8°E–32°E) and (B) Western Europe (35°N–60°N, 10°W–30°E). Red boxes indicate the latitude–longitude bounds used for subsetting gridded data. Analysis is restricted to land grid cells only.

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Figure S3. Multi-model projections of global and regional temperature and terrestrial carbon dynamics showing the individual model projections. (a) Change in global mean temperature (ΔT) relative to pre-industrial levels. Horizontal dashed lines indicate the 1.5 °C and 2.0 °C targets. (b) Global change in terrestrial carbon stock ($\Delta CLand$) and (c) Net Ecosystem Production (ΔNEP), both relative to the contemporary baseline (1985–2014). (d, e) Regional projections for Central Africa and (f, g) Western Europe showing $\Delta CLand$ and ΔNEP , respectively.

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 935 **Figure S4:** Global anomalies in net ecosystem productivity (ΔNEP), net primary productivity (ΔNPP),
 936 and heterotrophic respiration (ΔRh) (Pg C yr^{-1}) for 2020–2100 relative to the contemporary baseline
 937 (1985–2014) under four SSP scenarios. Solid lines represent the multi-model mean; shaded bands
 938 indicate inter-model spread. The horizontal dashed line marks zero. Ensemble sizes vary by variable
 939 and scenario: for ΔNEP and ΔRh , $n = 5$ (SSP1-1.9), $n = 9$ (SSP1-2.6), $n = 6$ (SSP5-3.4-OS), and $n = 9$
 940 (SSP5-8.5); for ΔNPP , $n = 5$ (SSP1-1.9), $n = 10$ (SSP1-2.6), $n = 7$ (SSP5-3.4-OS), and $n = 10$ (SSP5-
 941 8.5)
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